

Review article

3D-Printed OMFC-supercapacitor hybrids for sustainable energy recovery

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ABSTRACT

Over the past 14 years, osmotic microbial fuel cell (OMFC) technology has been applied in the purification of drinking water, bioenergy production, environmental monitoring and resource recovery at the bench scale. However, it still faces significant challenges in industrial implementation and scaling towards commercialization. These challenges include complex reactor design for handling high reaction volume, long start-up time, costly and laborious fabrication processes for large-scale systems. Interestingly, to overcome these challenges, incorporating 3-dimensional printing (3DP) technology with OMFC seems a viable and promising approach. Furthermore, 3D-printed bio-anodes could offer quick start-up in the current generation using OMFC without any time lags. Also, a stacked OMFC-coupled supercapacitor (SC) system can be easily designed using 3DP technology to generate and store a significant amount of bioelectricity and produce pure water from wastewater. To the best of the author's knowledge, this is the first review paper that specifically highlights the application of 3DP in developing a stacked OMFC system coupled with SC to harvest and store a significant amount of bioenergy in the form of electricity. Similarly, one noteworthy aspect of 3DP technology is its consistent production capabilities, that allow OMFC systems to be scaled up by building multiple stacks of OMFC units without wasting materials and completely free from human error. This review further aims to present the current state and status of the 3DP application to advance OMFC-SC and explore potential future applications of it along with global energy demand.

1. Introduction

Rapid population growth, urbanization and industrial development are driving up the world's energy demand and climate change and water scarcity are serious environmental concern [1,2]. A move towards sustainable and renewable energy sources like solar, wind, biomass and fuel cells are being driven by the energy sector's continued significant contribution to greenhouse gas emissions (GHG). Energy storage technologies are crucial because many of these alternatives are constrained by their erratic output and reliance on external factors. At the same time, the world's water crisis requires effective wastewater treatment technologies [2–5]. Among these, membrane-based separation techniques forward osmosis (FO) in particular have drawn interest due to their high selectivity and low energy needs [6–9]. Osmotic microbial fuel cell (OMFC) systems, which combine the advantages of clean water and bioelectricity generation, are created as FO is

integrated with microbial fuel cell (MFC) [10–13]. OMFC have limitations in terms of scalability, slow start-up times and complex design, despite their potential. Three-dimensional printing (3DP) has recently become a potent tool for overcoming these obstacles by making it possible to fabricate OMFC components quickly, cheaply and with customization [14–18]. In order to address the issues of energy and water, by using 3DP technology can transform OMFC design, specifically through stacked configurations in conjunction with supercapacitors (SC) [19].

The direct digital-to-physical conversion of intricate, customized architectures with little manual intervention is made possible by 3DP, in contrast to conventional fabrication techniques like moulding, machining, or layering discrete components [15,16,20–22]. This method makes it possible to precisely control surface characteristics, porosity and geometry all of which are crucial elements in microbial electrochemical systems like OMFC [16,17]. Conventional techniques

Abbreviations: OMFC, Osmotic Microbial Fuel Cell; SC, Supercapacitor; 3DP, Three-Dimensional Printing; AI, Artificial Intelligence; ML, Machine Learning; EET, Extracellular Electron Transfer; DET, Direct Electron Transfer; PNIPAm, PolyN-isopropylacrylamide; MFC, Microbial Fuel Cell; OCP, Open Circuit Potential; PD, Power Density; CD, Current Density; CRR, Capacitance Retention Rate; SEM, Scanning Electron Microscopy; DIW, Direct Ink Writing; FDM, Fused Deposition Modeling; SLA, Stereolithography; DLP, Digital Light Processing; AJP, Aerosol Jet Printing; IJP, Inkjet Printing; MM-3DP, Multi-Material 3D Printing; COD, Chemical Oxygen Demand; GHG, Greenhouse Gas; OLR, Organic Loading Rate; PCL, Polycaprolactone; EFD, Electric-Field-Driven

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frequently lack this spatial flexibility and precision, which results in uneven performance and laborious assembly procedures. On the other hand, 3DP can create monolithic, integrated structures in a single step, such as reactor chambers, electrodes and separators, guaranteeing improved alignment, lower internal resistance and fewer mechanical failure points.

Additionally, 3DP facilitates the use of biological or functional materials, including porous carbon composites, conductive polymers and even living microbial inks [17]. These characteristics are essential for improving power generation and water recovery in OMFC because they speed up biofilm formation and enhance microbial-electrode interactions [19]. Rapid prototyping and customization for particular wastewater streams or power requirements are encouraged by the modularity of 3DP, which also makes scale-up, stacking and design iteration simple. These benefits make 3DP a revolutionary tool in microbial electrochemical technologies [23]. It provides solutions that are easier to replicate, faster to fabricate and more performance-optimized than their conventionally manufactured counterparts.

OMFC technology has drawn increasing attention owing to the growing demand for clean water and bioenergy sources. OMFC is a novel approach that combines electrochemistry and microbiological metabolism for a range of high-value applications [12,24,25]. The OMFC process (Fig. 1), that combines the benefits of both FO (transport of water molecules across a membrane from low to high osmotic pressure) and MFC (breakdown of organic matter to produce protons and electrons) can generate pure water and bioelectricity. Therefore, OMFC has demonstrated a wide range of applications, including (1) the generation of bioenergy through processes such as biomethane production in anaerobic digesters, bioelectricity generation in MFC and biohydrogen generation in microbial electrolysis cell (MEC); (2) manufacturing essential substances such as hydrogen peroxide; (3) nutrient recovery from urine; and (4) use of biosensors to desalinate saline water [6,21,26].

More focus has recently been placed on improving system performance through reactor configuration optimization, creative aeration methods and improved membrane selection in OMFC study. Researcher focus on OMFC used for activated sludge thickening achieved a maximum power density of 1704.6 W m^{-3} , more than twice as much as conventional MFCs (762.3 W m^{-3}) and a total chemical oxygen demand (COD) removal of 90.7% [27]. Another study that used a siphon-driven self-aeration mechanism found that OMFC significantly reduced membrane impedance (around $5 \Omega \text{ cm}^{-2}$), achieved a stable water flux (around $1.8 \text{ L m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$) and removed about 85.7% of COD although operating continuously and saving about \$ 0.033 per litre of treated wastewater [28]. Additionally, it was demonstrated that membrane

cleaning techniques, especially those based on NaClO, could improve power density by up to 2.7 times and restore up to 91.6% flux recovery, primarily due to better proton advection across the FO membrane [29]. These advancements demonstrate how OMFC can outperform traditional MFCs in terms of energy recovery and treatment efficiency once combined with innovative material configurations and operational advancements.

Recently, electrodes and terracotta membranes were created by 3-dimensional printing (3DP) stacking plant-MFC (PMFC) using Fusion-360 technology [30]. The study used different stacking patterns of PMFC, such as a combination of series and parallel. Since stacking cells together expands the overall surface area that can be used for electrochemical reactions, however, it also raises the system's overall resistance, thereby significantly impacting power generation. The stacked PMFC achieved open circuit potential (OCP), power density (PD), current density (CD) and a current of 0.442 V , 0.6 mW.m^{-2} , 5.5 mA.m^{-2} and 0.18 mA , respectively [30]. Another 3DP study produced electrodes and a reactor body using fused deposition modeling (FDM) technology [31]. The effect of operating conditions on power production was understood by examining various MFC reactor configurations. Single and double-chamber reactors were constructed from biocompatible polylactic acid (PLA). Three electrodes have been printed with conductive PLA: an anode for the single chamber configuration and a cathode and anode for the double chamber configuration. The study achieved OCP, PD and CD in a double-chamber and single-chamber MFC system (1.01 V , 18.8 mW.m^{-2} and 48 mA.cm^{-2}) and (0.61 V , 16.5 mW.m^{-2} and 44 mA.cm^{-2}), respectively. The main reasons for the better performance of double chamber MFC compared to single chamber were: (a) the use of cation exchange membrane (CEM) separating the analyte and catholyte and; (b) potassium permanganate catholyte might likely better balanced the redox reactions that occurred in the reactor. The subsequent 3DP study used digital light processing (DLP) technology to create porous anode electrodes layer by layer [32]. A porous type of electrode provides more surface area for bacterial growth. The prepared porous anode has pore sizes from 100 to $500 \mu\text{m}$ and a porosity of 95%. A standard carbon cloth and a porous electrode with a 3D-printed matrix structure were used to assess the performance. Due to high bacterial cell density on the surface of the porous electrode, the single chamber MFC achieved OCP, PD, CD and current of 1.2 V , 233.5 mW.m^{-2} , 0.18 mA.m^{-2} and 0.018 mA respectively. Such electrodes allow excellent bacterial adhesion and growth owing to porous surface. In a recent study, living bacterial ink in 3DP Nordson-Electric-Field-Driven was used as a printing tip at a writing speed of 1.16 mm.s^{-1} [17]. The work demonstrated use of different bacterial species, such as *E. coli*, *Shewanella oneidensis*, *Pseudomonas putida*, yeast

Fig. 1. Schematic of FO, MFC and OMFC system. FO = forward osmosis; MFC = microbial fuel cell; OMFC = osmotic microbial fuel cell.

cells, etc, mixed with sodium alginate and cellulose with acetylene carbon black to prepare ink. The bacterial activity post 3DP examined using confocal microscope image (CMI) indicated presence of live bacteria with intact membranes and dead bacteria with broken membranes. The CMI analysis showed that bacterial cells possess good survival rate during 3DP process. The anode electrode containing biofilm was attached to the platinum wire and placed into the 2-chamber MFC system. The findings indicated that the resultant MFC achieved OCP, PD and CD of 0.85 V, 8.5 W.m⁻³ and 55 A.m⁻³, respectively [17]. In the 3DP bioanode, CMI exhibited both healthy and damaged cells. According to similar extrusion-based microbial ink systems, nozzle size, shear stress and ink formulation can affect cell viability right after printing, which can range from approximately 75–97%. After a few hours of incubation, survival usually returns to > 90%. This implies that the good survival rate during 3DP that has been reported probably translates into bacterial viability above early-generation test thresholds (≥80%), which is regarded as adequate to maintain OMFC activity [33,34].

The 3DP technology can offer a compelling substitute for laborious biofilm development processes. In particular, items that are 3D printed with microbes may attain a thick biofilm because of the adhesion of cells during the process [17]. Because living cells involved in the 3DP process attain higher cell density on the surface of the electrode [17,21]. The 3DP process significantly shortens the bioelectrode start-up time because the bacterial colony stays alive and partially pre-attached [17,23]. In contrast to the around 2–5 days normally needed for biofilm formation on conventional electrodes like carbon cloth or graphite rods under similar conditions, researcher reported that bioelectrodes fabricated with embedded live bacteria using extrusion-based 3DP initiated measurable current production within 9–12 h [17,23,35]. In a recent study, for 2-chamber MFC, an X-shaped matrix-type electrode served as the anode and urine as a feed material [36]. Using 3DP technology, the following 2 electrodes were created, with the surfaces of titanium (Ti) and stainless steel (SS) alloys coated with polyaniline (PANI) through electropolymerization. PANI-coated 3DP-SS and 3DP-Ti have a porosity of 87.36% and 81.42%, respectively. PANI-SS-based MFC achieved PD and CD of 0.934 W.m⁻³ and 4.831 A.m⁻³ respectively whereas PANI-Ti-based MFC obtained PD and CD of 0.798 W.m⁻³ and 4.466 A.m⁻³ respectively [36]. Another study demonstrated the use of an FDM-based technique to produce a 3DP MFC with and without a ceramic membrane [37]. The design of MFC resembles a cubic structure that has an anode and cathode with surface area of 158.5 and 96.2 cm², respectively. The study showed that biofilm formation was faster in the membrane-less MFC than relative to MFC with the membrane. The MFC with membrane achieved PD and normalized energy recovery (NER) of 8.0 W.m⁻³ and 0.69 kWh.m⁻³ respectively. On the contrary, the MFC without membrane achieved PD and NER of 8.1 W.m⁻³ and 0.57 kWh.m⁻³ respectively. Recent literature has shown that FDM-based 3DP was used to produce coin-size MFC [38]. The work investigated the impact of the thickness and pore size of widely used filter papers of varying grades on MFC performance. Polycaprolactone filament was used in FDM 3DP to create the borders of paper MFC. Numerous electrochemical studies have been performed to comprehend the behavior of different MFCs with different separators. MFC with grade-6 cellulose filter paper was found to be the most effective separator, providing a stable voltage of 0.48 V. The coin size MFC generated maximum OCP, PD and CD of 0.6 V, 0.011 mW.cm⁻² and 0.09 mA.cm⁻², respectively. Another similar study demonstrates the production of paper-based MFC using wax-based 3DP ink, with paper serving as the substrate and wax-based CEM [39]. Graphite and activated carbon are used as the anode electrode materials. The paper-based MFC generates maximum OCP, PD and CD of 0.49 V, 4.6 mW.m⁻² and 119 mA.m⁻² respectively.

In 3DP technology, mostly FDM and direct ink writing (DIW) techniques have been used for manufacturing 3D components, including electrode assembly for MFC systems [16,18,21,40]. Another

study on FO membrane used the FDM technique to create a 3DP-FO membrane to achieve a water flux with the FO module of 6.62 L.m⁻².h⁻¹ [6]. The new convergence of OMFC systems and 3D printing is compiled and examined in this review in a unique way, with a focus on stacked OMFC units that are integrated with SC. Although there have been general reviews of 3DP or MFCs, none have examined how additive manufacturing is transforming the OMFC-SC architectures performance, scalability and fabrication. This article main goal is to present new developments, relevant 3D printing techniques and performance standards. It also lays out a plan for taking 3DP-enabled OMFC-SC technology from lab to practical implementation.

2. SC technology

SC, also known as electrochemical capacitors or ultracapacitors, store electric charge via 2 main mechanisms: Electrostatic adsorption, known as electrical double-layer capacitance (EDLC) and fast surface redox reactions, known as pseudocapacitance [41,42]. Depending on the dominant charge storage mechanism, SC are classified as either EDLC or pseudocapacitors. In EDLC, charge is stored by the formation of an electric double layer at the electrode/electrolyte interface without any Faradaic (electron transfer) reactions. In contrast, pseudocapacitors involve Faradaic reactions at the interface, contributing to additional capacitance [42,43]. SC are increasingly considered for replacing or supplementing batteries in various applications. Compared to conventional batteries, SC have lower energy density but excel in power delivery, offering rapid bursts of energy. Their advantages include high power density, fast charge/discharge rates, long cycle life and enhanced safety. These features enable shorter charging times, more efficient integration with renewable energy and the potential use of environmental friendly materials [43–45]. SC are widely employed in commercial systems such as regenerative braking in vehicles and elevators, memory backup in electronics, energy grid stabilization and electric buses [46].

Structurally, a typical SC consists of 2 porous electrodes separated by an ion-permeable membrane (separator) and immersed in an aqueous, organic, or ionic liquid electrolyte. Once voltage is applied, positive and negative ions migrate toward the respective electrodes, forming an electric double layer at the interface [41,44,47]. Hybrid SC, typically asymmetric in design, combine pseudocapacitive materials with EDLC materials. This hybridization leverages the high specific capacitance of pseudocapacitors and the excellent cycling stability of EDLC, resulting in improved energy density without compromising power performance. The performance of an SC is primarily dictated by the electrode material and it is assessed through comprehensive electrochemical characterization. Key parameters include specific capacitance, equivalent series resistance, capacitance retention, leakage current, self-discharge, energy density and power density [41,47]. These performance metrics vary depending on the electrode materials and electrolytes used [43,45,48–53]. Table 1 summarizes the electrochemical performance of recently studied 3DP SC system.

Recent research on 3DP-SC has spurred innovation by showcasing high-performance energy storage and environmentally friendly materials that are pertinent to OMFC-SC integration. Using dopamine-grafted activated carbon electrodes and a deep eutectic solvent electrolyte, Researchers created a fully biocompatible device that greatly outperformed previous fully-printed devices, achieving a specific capacitance of 96 F.g⁻¹ and an energy density of 22 Wh.kg⁻¹ [61]. Similarly, using catechin-hydrated activated carbon and a printed green electrolyte, a bio-inspired SC achieved 75 F.g⁻¹ at 1 mV.s⁻¹, showcasing sustainable electrode chemistry with cutting-edge synthesis [62]. The viability of printed pseudocapacitive electrodes with superior gravimetric and volumetric performance has been confirmed by the achievement of areal capacitance up to 44 F.cm⁻² on the electro structural front using 3D-printed graphene aerogel scaffolds loaded with MnO₂, as well as maintaining ion diffusion even at high mass

Table 1
Summarizes the electrochemical performance of recently reported 3DP SC systems

Types of 3DP	Positive electrode Electrolyte Negative electrode	Capacitance@ CD	CRR (CD)	ED	PD	Ref.
FDM	NiCo-LDH@3D-PE 2M KOH acid-treated carbon cloth	3.14 F cm ⁻² @ 5 mA cm ⁻²	93% after 10,000 (100 mA cm ⁻²)	1.26 mW h cm ⁻²	4.74 mW cm ⁻²	[54]
Extrusion 3DP	AC PVA-H ₃ PO ₄ AC N@ZnCoSe ₂ -MXene 70% (w/w) polyester resin + 20% (w/w) EMIMBF ₄ 1.0% (w/w) LiTf salt N@ZnCoSe ₂ -MXene Pristine graphene PVA-LiOH Pristine graphene	3.48 F g ⁻¹ or 328.95 mF cm ⁻² @ 2.5 mA 19.36 F g ⁻¹ @ 1 A g ⁻¹	90% after 500 (2.5 mA) 83.7% after 6000	0.484 W h kg ⁻¹ 2.69 W h kg ⁻¹	15.01 W kg ⁻¹ 43.2 W kg ⁻¹	[55] [56]
3DP Micro-SC		1.57 F cm ⁻² @ 2 mA cm ⁻²	87.6 after 4500 cycles @ 10 mA	0.0512 mW h cm ⁻²	0.968 mW cm ⁻²	[57]
Stereo Lithography	PEGDA: PEDOT resin PVA-KCl PEGDA: PEDOT resin	11.4 mF cm ⁻² @ 0.005 mA cm ⁻²	90% after 500 cycles @0.01 mA cm ⁻²	0.00068 mW h cm ⁻²	0.002 mW cm ⁻²	[58]
Inkjet printing Micro-SC	NM/NC2S PVA KOH rGO	983.9 F cm ⁻³ @0.5 mA cm ⁻²	98% after 25,000 @2.5 mA cm ⁻²	342.4 mW h cm ⁻³	15.4 W cm ⁻³	[59]
3DP	DPBAC DES DPBAC	39 F g ⁻¹ @ 0.2 A g ⁻¹	87% after 10,000 @ 0.2 A g ⁻¹	22 W h kg ⁻¹	1835 kg ⁻¹	[45]
3DP	CHBAC DES CHBAC	37 F g ⁻¹ @ 0.2 A g ⁻¹	90.2% after 10,000 @ 0.2 A g ⁻¹	20.6 W h kg ⁻¹	520 W kg ⁻¹	[43]
3DP	DAC NaCl DAC	24 F g ⁻¹ @ 8 mA g ⁻¹	90% after 10,000 @ 0.08 A g ⁻¹	4 W h kg ⁻¹	58 W kg ⁻¹	[53]
3DP	carbon/CNF/CNC CNC/glycerol/NaCl graphite/activated carbon/CNF/CNC	25.6 F g ⁻¹ at 1 mV s ⁻¹	99% post 2000 at 0.4 A g ⁻¹	0.88 W h kg ⁻¹	830 W h kg ⁻¹	[60]

AC = activated carbon; CD = current density; CRR = capacitance retention rate; EMIMBF₄ = 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium tetrafluoroborate; FDM = fused deposition modeling; LiTf = lithium trifluoromethanesulfonate; N@ZnCoSe₂-MXene = N-doped Zn-Co selenide nanowires in the presence of MXenes on woven carbon fiber surface; NiCo-LDH@3D-PE = nickel-cobalt layered double hydroxide electrode deposited on 3D-printed electrodes; NM/NC2S; NiCo₂S₄ = Nickel cobalt sulfide; PD = power density; PEDOT = Poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene); PEGDA = poly(ethylene glycol) diacrylate; rGO = reduced Graphene Oxide; SC = supercapacitor.

loadings [63]. In addition, hybrid MXene/cellulose inks enable direct ink writing of solid-state SC with an energy density of $101 \mu\text{Wh cm}^{-2}$, an aerial capacitance of 2 F cm^{-2} and an 85% capacitance retention after 5000 cycles [64].

It is important to note that 3DP SC using advanced electrode materials such as MXenes, transition metal oxides, carbon nanotubes and graphene typically exhibit superior electrochemical performance compared to those based on activated carbon. However, when prioritizing eco-friendliness, earth abundance, sustainability and cost, AC remains the preferred choice. This is due to its exceptionally high specific surface area ($\geq 2000 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$), excellent cycle stability ($\geq 100,000$ cycles) and cost-effectiveness (ranging between 10 and 20 EUR per kilogram). In our recently published work, we demonstrated a 3DP bio-based SC in that all components used in its fabrication - including the substrate made of PLA, the current collector using graphite ink, the catechin-modified activated carbon electrode (CHBAC ink), the electrolyte composed of a deep eutectic solvent (DES) and the separator made from cellulose are environmental friendly and derived from sustainable materials [62]. The developed SC demonstrated a stable operating voltage window of 2.0 V, retaining approximately 90.2% of their initial capacitance after 10,000 charge - discharge cycles. They delivered a specific energy 20.6 Wh kg^{-1} and a specific power of 560 W kg^{-1} .

Fully bio-based SCs offer an eco-friendly and sustainable solution for storing energy generated from MFCs. In our published work, the developed SC was designed to power low-power wireless systems. However, by integrating these SC in a stack, we can effectively match the energy output of the OMFC. In the following section, we have demonstrated the storage requirements of the SC once integrated with OMFC. It is worth emphasizing that DIW and IJP have shown significant potential in fabricating key components of SC, primarily due to their versatility in printing with multiple materials through tailored ink formulations. Despite these advancements, achieving a fully encapsulated or packaged device through a single-step printing process remains a major challenge. Nonetheless, 3DP stands out as a highly promising approach for SC development, offering opportunities for innovation in performance, cost-effectiveness and scalable manufacturing. Through continued research, this technology could pave the way for the fabrication of not only efficient SC but also integrated energy systems. Although the path to commercialization may still be long, the future market potential for 3DP SC, batteries and other electronic systems is undeniably strong.

3. Stacked OMFC-SC system

According to the most recent Scopus data, around 132 research/review articles have been published to date, covering a variety of OMFC characteristics and operating conditions [65,66]. None of these publications deal with implementing and scaling the OMFC system for energy recovery and wastewater treatment. Standalone OMFC unit can produce only relatively small electrical potentials, a maximum of 1.1 V (theoretically), through electrochemical reactions [67]. Presently, the primary issues with MFC technology are its low voltage output and high internal resistance. As a result, a single OMFC produces little power that is being used directly to power even low-power electronic devices like light-emitting diodes (LEDs) and wireless sensor radios [66,68]. The cells are stacked or connected in series/parallel to generate enough voltage to power external electronic appliances. Notably, at the very least, these devices require an operating voltage of 2–5 V and their power consumption may reach from 1 to 5 W [66].

MFC systems produce current and power at a rate that is more than 3 orders of magnitude lower than traditional hydrogen or methanol-fueled fuel cells [68]. Therefore, a clever design must be used to deliver the high-power pulses necessary to power devices after harvesting the produced low-energy pulses. Electrochemical energy storage devices known as SC can provide high specific power of up to 10 kW.kg^{-1} at the necessary energy level [69]. Therefore, multiple OMFC units must be connected in a stacked configuration to attain the same output. An external electronic

circuit system can then be used to increase the obtained voltage. Using multiple units, the biological fuel cells can be connected to form stack configurations that are either hydraulically or electrically powered. Depending on the applications of the generated power output, electrodes in the stacked arrangement are connected either in series or parallel to enhance the voltage or current output respectively, from cells [66,70,71].

Fig. 2 shows the schematic of the stacked OMFC-SC system. A single OMFC consists of 2 electrodes separated by an FO membrane. Anaerobic bacteria degrade organic matter in the anode compartment to produce protons and electrons. Protons travel from the anode to the cathode through the FO membrane and electrons travel through an external circuit and combine with atmospheric oxygen in the cathode compartment to produce water. The aerobic compartment also contains a salt solution that has higher osmotic pressure than the anode compartment and can extract water from it. In this way, the OMFC system performs better than the MFC system [8,72]. The following reactions take place at the anode (1), (3) and cathode (2), (4) using acetate and glucose as substrates, respectively [26,73].

Possible reactions on the anodic side:

Possible reactions on the cathodic side:

In 1911, Potter was the first researcher to develop the idea of producing electricity through the breakdown of organic compounds [74]. However, this idea was not well received because of the lower power generation [74,75]. The first significant development occurred in 1931, once Barnet Cohen connected several MFCs in series mode to produce 35 V [76]. The study stated that the maximum PD and OCP were obtained to be 20.2 W.m^{-3} and 0.810 V, respectively. Recently, the average power output of the stacked wetland MFCs ranged from $0.03 \pm 0.01 \text{ mW}$ (single pot) to $0.11 \pm 0.05 \text{ mW}$ (stacked connection of 5 pots) was observed over 60-days of operating period, with no voltage reversal observed in the design [77]. The wetland MFC produces a maximum PD of 9.02 mW.m^{-2} with 15 pots connected in a stacked configuration. It successfully charged a 1.2 V battery over a period of 30 h. Another study showed the amazing durability of PMFCs, functioning smoothly for more than 900 days without breaking down [78]. Although its performances were not as high as those found in the literature with other PMFCs, the power output was adequate to charge a 220 mF SC every 2 h from 2.6 to 3.6 V.

Recent work showed that the power output comparison revealed that the small reactors perform better than the large stacked MFCs (small and large MFCs having a capacity of 50 and 200 mL, respectively), with a maximum value of 25.7 W.m^{-3} [79]. This may be connected to a shorter electrode distance and the ceramic membrane's higher surface-area-to-volume ratio. Along with the total surface area of the anode electrode, the ceramic separator's type and thickness also impacted the power performance. According to the study, a greater anode electrode area results in a higher power output. The 560 MFCs stack's compact design demonstrated a power output of up to 245 mW. Another study demonstrated how MFC stacks could be used to treat wastewater with simultaneous electricity generation from swine wastewater in both series and parallel circuit modes [80]. The parallel and series connections approached a maximum PD of 175.7 W.m^{-2} at (0.38 V and 42.8 mA) and 0.067 W.m^{-2} at (1.1 V and 5.9 mA). The author achieved higher electrical performance in the parallel connection than in the series connection.

Recently, the study reported use of 28 ceramic separators stacked MFC systems connected in parallel, having a total volume of 1 L [81].

Fig. 2. Schematic of OMFC-SC system. OMFC = osmotic microbial fuel cell; SC = supercapacitor.

The stacked ceramic MFC achieved maximum OCP, PD CD and current of 0.6 V 10.60 W.m⁻³, 72.1 A.m⁻³ and 50 A, respectively. In another study, a voltage boost converter circuit was used for charging a 250 mF storage SC using 3 MFC-SC operating continuously [82]. A recent study showed low-cost earthen membranes in the stacked MFC system connected in parallel [83]. A 36 L pilot-scale setup was installed at the residence site to treat domestic wastewater and generate power simultaneously for decentralized application. The setup was used for 92 days and generated voltage and current of 4.1 V and 43.7 mA, respectively. A critical challenge to harvest useful power from MFC stacks is to prevent voltage reversal, resulting in the polarity of one or more cells and a loss of power generation. Fuel starvation causes voltage reversal, that in turn causes loss in bacterial activity and variation in internal resistance. This phenomenon frequently manifests in stacked MFCs, connected in series and run in fed-batch mode or during an abrupt shift in fuel demand [84–86]. The phenomenon of current reversal occurred once MFC modules stacked in a parallel configuration experienced a change in the direction of current flow, but their polarity stayed constant [84,87].

In stacked OMFC systems, voltage reversal is a major issue, especially in series configurations where an uneven fuel distribution or an imbalance in internal resistance can cause some cells to polarize in the opposite direction. Recent studies have introduced a number of experimental strategies to address this issue [80,88–91]. The researchers created a dual-layer cathode structure consisting of an outer layer that limits oxygen and a hydrophilic catalytic layer. In order to stabilize redox reactions and lessen the possibility of voltage reversal during stack operation, this architecture reduced excessive oxygen diffusion into the cathode [88,92]. Other researchers use SC buffer was incorporated by into their power management system for stacked MFCs that was based on maximum power point tracking (MPPT) [93].

Another study demonstrated that stacked MFCs perform much better and have a lower chance of voltage reversal when hydrodynamic flow is optimized. According to their research, independent hydrodynamic flow coupled with a parallel electrical connection generated 3 times as much power as dependent flow [94]. The system ensured

consistent energy output and prolonged operational stability by effectively absorbing short voltage dips and preventing weaker cells from entering reverse polarity. These advancements demonstrate how electrochemical design and electronic control can collaborate to effectively address voltage reversal by fusing cathode material engineering and intelligent energy harvesting, paving the way for more dependable and expandable MFC systems.

Theoretically, the simplified parallel circuit model's analysis indicated that the OCV differences between MFC modules and the applied external resistance value directly influenced reversal of current. The experimental results support this theory, showing that reversal current only occurred in MFC modules with lower OCP [95]. The wastewater treatment was monitored using COD study in the above-mentioned studies. The COD depends on the hydraulic retention time (HRT) and PD achieved by the MFC system. However, HRT and PD are more, the MFC or OMFC system's COD removal efficiency is higher than the less HRT and PD. If PD is increased quickly (a function of biofilm growth), then the COD removal efficiency is higher in a short time [72]. Tables 2 and 3 provide an overview of the stacked and 3DP MFC systems, respectively.

4. 3D printing technology

Additive manufacturing (AM), another name for 3DP, has expanded quickly in recent years. In brief, 3DP uses computer-aided design (CAD) models to create 3-dimensional structures by superimposing materials [15,22,101]. This method reduces the need for human involvement and makes it possible to quickly and precisely create complex structures and devices with intricate geometries [26,40]. Due to these positive attributes, 3DP has been used in a number of industries, including the arts, aerospace, medical implants and industrial prototype printing. Additionally, 3DP has been incorporated into a number of energy-generating devices, such as solar cells and batteries. Since 3DP is becoming more and more popular and useful, it has recently been used to fabricate different parts of metal-oxide thermocouples, such as reactor bodies, electrodes and membranes [18,21,32,37,40].

Table 2
Tabular representation of stacked MFC systems connected either in series or parallel

Types of system	PD ($W.m^{-2}$)	CD ($mA.cm^{-2}$)	OCP (mV)	Current (mA)	Remarks	Ref.
Wetland stacked MFC	0.009	–	–	–	5 pot connected	[77]
Series stacked MFC	–	–	300	0.3–0.4	Voltage reversal study	[87,96]
Stacked MFC	–	0.1–0.14	400 – 500	–	–	–
Parallel stacked small-size MFC	20 ^a	–	–	–	Anode volume: 50 mL	[79]
Parallel stacked large-size MFC	7.0 ^a	–	–	–	Anode volume: 200 mL	–
Series stacked MFC	0.067	–	2100	5.90	5 units are used in this study	[80]
Parallel stacked MFC	175.7	–	–	42.8	–	–
Parallel stacked ceramic membrane MFC	10.60 ^a	72.1 ^a	200–600	40–50 ^a	28 unit connected	[81]
Parallel stacked earthen membrane MFC	0.023 ^a	0.14 ^a	803	43.7	4 units having a total working volume of 36 L	[83]

CD = current density; MFC = microbial fuel cell; – = no data available; OCP = open circuit potential; PD = power density.

^a Unit of PD, CD, OCP and Current: $W.m^{-3}$, $A.m^{-3}$, V and A respectively.

3DP techniques are typically divided in 7 primary categories based on the deposition methods and curing processes used for electrodes, current collectors and electrolytes [102]. 3DP methods are categorized in 7 major types, each offering unique benefits and application potentials. These include: (i) Binder jetting; (ii) directed energy deposition; (iii) powder bed fusion techniques like SLS and selective laser melting (SLM); (iv) sheet lamination processes such as laminated object manufacturing; (v) vat photopolymerization, including DLP and stereolithography (SLA); (vi) material jetting technologies, for example, inkjet printing (IJP), aerosol jet printing (AJP) and electrohydrodynamic (EHD) jet printing; and (vii) material extrusion methods like FDM and DIW. Among these, techniques such as DLP, AJP, IJP, FDM, SLA and DIW are commonly adopted for OMFC-SC fabrication, owing to their compatibility with the necessary materials and structural requirements [37,101,103–108]. The key distinctions between these 3DP methods are qualitatively summarized in Table 4. Additionally, Fig. 3 represent schematics of different 3DP technologies.

4.1. 3DP in OMFC-SC

3DP has the potential to revolutionize OMFC/MFC components, according to recent additive manufacturing research in energy-related domains. The design of microbial electrodes may be influenced by the

mechanically robust, high-precision battery electrodes that researchers have recently presented [109]. Another researcher explains 3D-printed scaffolds that are hierarchically porous and have good transport dynamics. These design features are directly applicable to electrodes that support biofilms [110]. Similar studies clarify that 3D-printed customized Nb_2O_5/Ti electrodes exhibit chemical resilience and microbial compatibility, which are essential characteristics for long-term OMFC operation [111]. All of these studies support the idea that additive manufacturing offers significant benefits over traditional fabrication methods in microbial electrochemical systems due to its control over porosity, material composition and structural stability.

On the contrary, nanomaterials have the potential to significantly improve the functional performance, mechanical strength and printability of parts made using additive manufacturing. Recently, researcher shows that adding nano- Al_2O_3 , MgO, or Fe_2O_3 to cementitious extrusion inks greatly enhanced rheological behavior, flow stability and structural integrity after printing of particular note was the optimal dosing at 3 to 4 weight percent nano- Al_2O_3 and 4 weight percent nano- Fe_2O_3 , which decreased porosity and improved layer cohesion [112]. As with clay-based 3DP materials, stable addition of nano silica and polypropylene fibres improved print consistency and decreased mechanical anisotropy, both of which are necessary to preserve consistent conductivity and longevity in printed bioelectrode matrices [113].

Table 3
Summary of different 3DP stacked MFC systems

Types of system	PD ($mW.m^{-2}$)	CD ($mA.m^{-2}$)	OCP (mV)	Current (mA)	Applications of 3DP	Error Range/SD (%)	Ref.
3DP MFC	252	750–850	–	–	Electrode	–	[97]
3DP single and double chamber MFC	16	45	561–610	0.025	Reactor body and electrodes	± 5	[31]
3DP stacked PMFC	18.5	48	950–1000	0.062	–	–	–
3DP stacked MFC	0.1–0.6	1.5–5.5	442	0.08–0.18	Electrodes with terracotta membrane	–	[30]
3DP MFC	233.5	0.18	453–1200	0.018	Porous carbon anode	–	[32]
3DP MFC	0.006	0.005	250	–	Porous copper anode	–	[98]
3DP BES	–	9200–12,000	–	–	SiOC anode electrodes	–	[99]
3DP MFC	4.6	119	490	–	Paper-based with wax membrane	± 0.3	[39]
3DP MFC	–	0.5 ^a	200–500	0.2–0.3	Graphene electrodes	–	[18]
3DP MFC	0.011 ^a	0.04– 0.09 ^a	480–600	–	Paper-based coin size	–	[38]
3DP MFC	0.15–0.18 ^b	–	400–600	1–1.6	Anode electrode and membrane	± 10	[37]
3DP MFC (urine powered)	0.798–0.934 ^c	1–5.5 ^c	0.1–0.3 ^c	0.01–0.04 ^c	X-shaped Anode electrode	± 0.02	[36]
3DP MFC	8.5 ^c	55 ^c	0.85 ^c	–	Electrodes prepared by ink containing living bacterial cells	–	[17]
3DP stacked MFC	7.5 ^c	–	0.174 ^c	0.001–0.005 ^c	Reactor body and electrodes	–	[100]

CD = current density; MFC = microbial fuel cell; – = no data available; OCP = open circuit potential; PD = power density.

^a Unit of PD and CD: $mW.cm^{-2}$ and $mA.cm^{-2}$ respectively.

^b Unit of PD: mW.

^c Unit of PD, CD, OCP and Current: $W.m^{-3}$, $A.m^{-3}$, V and A respectively.

Table 4
Comparative summary of 3DP techniques for SC fabrication [102,115]

3D printing technique	Key benefits	Limitations	Resolution (μm)	Ink viscosity (cP)
DLP	High-speed fabrication, exceptional precision, efficient for intricate structures	Limited to compatible photo-curable materials; relatively costly supplies	≈ 15	Not specified
AJP	Effective on uneven surfaces, works with a broad range of ink viscosities, fine features achievable	Equipment is expensive; quality control can be difficult; overspray possible	≈ 10	1–2500
IJP	Highly precise, efficient material usage, well-established commercial availability	Susceptible to nozzle clogging; viscosity limits restrict ink diversity	≈ 20	10–20
FDM	Fast print speeds, accessible hardware, compatible with large structures	Poor resolution; limited to thermoplastics; surface finish may be rough	50–200	Not specified
SLA	Ultra-high detail, smooth surfaces, customizable geometries	Slow scan speed; high resin and equipment costs; limited to specific materials	0.25–10	Not specified
DIW	Versatile material compatibility, no need for masks or molds, high active material loading possible	Demands specific ink rheology; use of binders may reduce electrical output	≈ 1	10^2 – 10^8

AJP = aerosol jet printing; DIW = direct ink writing; DLP = digital light processing; FDM = fused deposition modeling; IJP = inkjet printing; SC = supercapacitor; SLA = stereolithography.

4.2. 3DP resolution limitations

The fidelity, reproducibility and electrochemical performance of printed electrodes and membranes used in OMFC-SC systems are all significantly influenced by the spatial resolution of 3DP techniques. Table 4 illustrates how resolution differs greatly between 3DP techniques, ranging from much coarser features in fused deposition modeling (FDM, 50–200 μm) to submicron accuracy in stereolithography (SLA, 0.25–10 μm). The ability to accurately reproduce complex features, like microchannels or porous gradients, during printing is directly impacted by this variation. DIW ($\approx 1 \mu\text{m}$) and AJP ($\approx 10 \mu\text{m}$) have high resolutions, which makes them appropriate for printing fine-textured electrodes with high electroactive surface area and distinct architectures that facilitate effective electron transfer and microbial colonization. On the other hand, because of uneven surfaces or large pore sizes, the relatively coarse resolution of FDM may prevent uniform biofilm formation. Furthermore, poor resolution can lead to impurities like delamination, blocked pores, or uneven catalyst dispersion in membranes, which will ultimately reduce ionic conductivity and system efficiency. Therefore, one of the main obstacles to guaranteeing design fidelity and repeatability in OMFC-SC

fabrication is still the mismatch between the desired feature size and the achievable print resolution. Future research should address this by focussing on developing hybrid strategies (e.g., combining DIW with SLA) and optimizing print parameters (e.g., nozzle diameter, curing conditions) to balance material compatibility, resolution and throughput for bio electrochemical applications [15,16,21,40,101,103,114].

The development of high-performance 3DP electrodes and spacer (FO) for OMFC–SC hybrid systems requires appropriate material selection. Major factors include electrical conductivity, mechanical stability, surface chemistry and compatibility with various 3DP techniques. Materials with favorable band structures, like graphene, carbon nanotubes (CNTs) and Ti_3C_2 MXene, improve extracellular electron transfer (EET) from electroactive biofilms and make electron transport more effective [116–118]. Surface chemistry is also significant; functional groups like amine, hydroxyl, or fluorine encourage redox reactions at the electrode interface and facilitate microbial adhesion. Conductive polymers such as Poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene):Polystyrene sulfonate (PEDOT:PSS) and polyaniline (PANI), offer additional redox-active sites and biocompatibility, that enhance system performance even more [119,120]. Mechanically, to maintain electrode integrity over time, materials must be both flexible and structurally stable.

3DP techniques nomenclature: FDM: Fused deposition modelling; SLA: Stereolithography apparatus; DLP: Digital light processing; 2PP: two-photon polymerization; SLS: Selective layer sintering; MJ: Material jetting; PBF: Powder bed fusion

Fig. 3. Different types of 3DP technology based on feed materials used [15,21,101,103,105,107].

Table 5
Theoretical basis for material selection in hybrid interfaces and 3DP OMFC-SC system

Materials	3DP Methods	Band structure/ Conductivity	Surface chemistry	Mechanical properties	Applications in OMFC	Ref.
Graphene composites	DIW and SLA	Semi-metal, high conductivity ($\sim 10^6$ S m^{-1})	π -conjugated surface, biofilm adhesion	High tensile strength, printable with binders	Biofilm growth support; high e^- transfer pathways	[116,126]
Graphite-PLA composites	FDM	Low to moderate conductivity; carbon-rich filaments	Low surface energy; post-treatment needed	Rigid, recyclable thermoplastic	Cost-effective 3DP; structural electrodes	[108,117,127]
Carbon Nanotubes	DIW, Extrusion-based	Metallic/semiconducting; high aspect ratio for conductivity	High surface area; functionalizable	Excellent flexibility and strength	DET; hierarchical porosity	[117,128]
Polyaniline	Inkjet, DIW, SLA	Conductive (10 – 200 S cm^{-1}); tunable redox behavior	Nitrogen-based redox sites; proton conductivity	Moderate mechanical flexibility	Redox mediation, pseudocapacitive integration	[119,123]
PEDOT:PSS	Inkjet, SLA	Moderate conductivity (10^2 – 10^3 S cm^{-1})	Hydrophilic, stable in water	Flexible, printable	Enhances bioelectrode interface, capacitance boost	[119,123]
MnO ₂ composites	SLA, DIW	Semiconducting; pseudocapacitive (0.26–2 eV bandgap)	Surface redox reactivity	Brittle; blended with carbon-based inks	Capacitive enhancement; anode/cathode composites	[121,122]
Ti ₃ C ₂ MXene	Inkjet, DIW	Metallic ($\sim 10^4$ S cm^{-1}); tunable surface terminations	OH, F groups promote electron/ion exchange	Flexible layers, printable in hydrogel matrices	Dual function: charge storage and microbial support	[118,124]

DET = direct electron transfer; DIW = direct ink writing; FDM = fused deposition modeling; OMFC = osmotic microbial fuel cell; PEDOT = poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene); PLA = polylactic acid; PSS = polystyrene sulfonate; SC = supercapacitor; SLA = stereolithography.

Despite being important for pseudocapacitive performance, materials such as MnO₂ are often incompatible with more robust materials like graphene or carbon nanotubes in composite matrices due to their inherent brittleness [121,122]. The way these materials work with 3DP techniques is equally important. Although FDM enables thermoplastic-based conductive filaments, like graphite-PLA composites, to be produced in large quantities, DIW and SLA enable the creation of intricate electrode geometries with conductive slurries and hydrogels [123]. Once combined, these material systems aid in achieving the dual objectives of biofilm formation and efficient charge storage. Once carefully chosen based on electronic structure, surface properties and printability, these enhance ion diffusion, interface conductivity, power density and energy recovery in OMFC-SC hybrid architectures [124,125]. Table 5 explain the theoretical basis for material selection in hybrid interface and 3DP OMFC-SC system.

4.3. 3DP materials for OMFC

4.3.1. Electrodes

Electrodes with improved structures and properties have been successfully produced using 3DP techniques [17,18,35]. The flexibility and easy use of the DIW and FDM methods set them apart from the other 3DP techniques. It is expected that more advanced printing methods will be developed for the production of electrodes as the 3DP technology evolves. Interestingly, electrode fabrication has undergone a tremendous revolution owing to 3DP. 3DP provides a novel way to address various issues with microbial electrochemical technologies by using 3DP electrode architecture designs, that significantly improve MFC performance and biocompatibility with electron-producing microbes. This is in contrast with the conventional 2D planar electrode structure [16].

Research community has shown great interest in developing electrodes with highly porous structures for optimal bacterial adhesion and excellent electrochemical performance for high current output. Notably, intricate macroporous 3DP electrode materials are appropriate for increasing the surface area for biofilm development and enhancing the electrochemical performance of OMFC. However, the main challenge lies in precisely manufacturing electrodes with geometrical complexities (such as porous electrodes) using conventional manufacturing processes. Researchers have recently investigated the potential of 3DP in fabricating prototype electrode materials for OMFC systems [32,36,98].

In addition to the electrodes and other physical components, electroactive microbes are crucial elements that influence the performance of OMFC. Complete enrichment of the anode or cathode biofilms can take a long time because of slow growth kinetics, that ultimately lengthens the reactor start-up time [25]. Anaerobic sewage sludge has been used as an inoculum source in several studies to accelerate the enrichment of electroactive biofilms [10]. Nonetheless, a novel strategy is required to develop electroactive biofilms quickly on electrode surface. Therefore, the synthesis of such bioanodes creates new avenues for high-performance OMFC [21,35,72]. A comparative overview of important 3DP parameters is given in Table 6 and the different characterization methods used to assess the performance of OMFC-SC systems are described in Table 7.

Three primary categories are used to classify electrodes Fig. 4(a–f): non-3DP, 3DP biotic and 3DP abiotic. Since electrodes are composed of non-living materials and usually have a less surface area than 3DP, non-3DP abiotic electrodes like graphite rods or traditional carbon cloth restrict the ability of bacteria to adhere to them and form biofilms. On the other hand, 3DP abiotic electrodes are made with additive manufacturing techniques, that enable customized geometries and porosity, even though they are also made of non-living materials. Due to the increased surface area, electrochemical interactions are more effective. The 3DP biotic electrode, the most sophisticated type shown in Fig. 4(e), integrates live bacterial cells straight into the printing process.

Table 6
Summary of the 3DP parameter that is helpful for printing various OMFC-SC system parts

3DP Technique	Electrode material	Nozzle diameter (mm)	Infill density (%)	Layer height (mm)	Print speed (mm s ⁻¹)	Porosity (%)	Ref.
FDM	Graphene/PLA composite	0.4	20–100	0.1–0.3	30–60	~50	[137]
DIW	Carbon ink with CNTs	0.2–0.6	-	0.2–0.4	5–20	> 70	[138,139]
SLA	Conductive resin + carbon black	Laser-spot ~0.1	Solid	0.025–0.1	-	~30	[140,141]
DLP	PEGDA + conductive fillers	Projector pixel ~0.05	Solid	0.05–0.1	-	20–40	[142,143]
JP	PEDOT:PSS + graphene oxide	~0.03–0.05	-	-	< 10	~15	[144,145]
AJP	Silver ink + CNTs	0.05–0.1 (aerosol stream)	-	-	< 5	~20	[146,147]

AJP = aerosol jet printing; DIW = direct ink writing; DLP = digital light processing; FDM = fused deposition modeling; LJP = inkjet printing; OMFC = osmotic microbial fuel cell; PEDOT = poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene); PLA = polylactic acid; PSS = polystyrene sulfonate; SC = supercapacitor; SLA = stereolithography.

High surface area and pre-existing microbial colonies are 2 benefits of these biotic electrodes that speed up start-up and promote direct electron transfer (DET). The morphological changes of electrode surfaces before and after 3D printing are depicted in Fig. 4(a, c, d and f), highlighting variations in texture, porosity and structure. These pictures demonstrate the improved surface characteristics of 3DP electrodes, which help to improve bacterial adhesion and electrochemical performance, in conjunction with schematic representations of microbial embedding.

Fig. 4(g) shows the schematic of DET and mediated electron transfer (MET) are the 2 main ways that electrons are transferred from electroactive microorganisms to the anode in OMFC systems known as extracellular electron transfer (EET), especially those that use 3DP electrodes [75,129,130]. DET entails a direct interaction between the electrode material and the microbial cell surface, frequently through conductive pili called nanowires or outer membrane cytochromes. Surface morphology, chemical functionality and conductivity are crucial design parameters because this process is heavily reliant on the microbial biofilm's compatibility and proximity to the electrode surface [97,131,132].

MET, on the other hand, uses redox-active molecules to transfer electrons from the microbial metabolic chain to the electrode. These molecules can be either naturally produced by microbes (endogenous mediators like flavins or phenazines) or added externally (exogenous mediators like neutral red or methylene blue). MET can add complexity and expense, but it is typically less reliant on microbial attachment. Although MET may profit from the incorporation of conductive polymer composites or redox-active materials in the printed architecture, DET is supported in 3DP systems by optimizing surface chemistry and porosity, that improves microbial adhesion and facilitates effective charge transfer. Enhancing the power output, stability and scalability of OMFC-SC hybrid systems require an understanding of and commitment to optimizing these mechanisms [97,132–136].

To improve electrochemical performance in 3DP OMFC-SC systems, electrode architecture optimization is essential. In bio-electrochemical systems, mass transfer kinetics, microbial colonization and ion transport pathways are all directly impacted by hierarchical porosity and tortuosity [129,153–156]. Although macropores help with microbial attachment and biofilm formation, an increase in interconnected micropores and mesopores within the printed electrode promotes improved ion and nutrient diffusion. The internal resistance and accessibility of electroactive sites can be greatly impacted by tortuosity, that is a representation of the complexity of diffusion pathways. Furthermore, the available reactive interface for electron transfer is determined by specific surface area as a function of pore structure and printing resolution. Integrating electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) to assess charge transfer resistance, double-layer capacitance and Warburg impedance associated with diffusion limitations is crucial to quantitatively establishing these relationships [157–159]. Important mechanistic insight in optimizing 3DP electrode designs for microbial electrochemical technologies would be provided by a parametric study that correlates electrode architecture (controlled via extrusion speed, layer height and infill density) with EIS results, cyclic voltammetry and power density outputs. This all-encompassing strategy will guarantee that performance-driven metrics, not just empirical observation, will inform the architectural decisions [159–161].

4.3.2. FO membrane

FO, a membrane treatment technique that is currently available, is drawing a lot of interest owing to its osmotic pressure difference-driven system that does not require the application of additional pressure. As a result, FO uses much less energy than the other separation methods including ultrafiltration, nanofiltration and RO [9,162]. FO has many benefits such as high rejection, less fouling, no external pressure, etc. Still, important issues need to be resolved. These problems include concentration polarization, membrane fouling, draw solute design and

Table 7
Overview of different characterization techniques use in OMFC-SC system [129,149–152]

Characterization techniques	Primary role	Property analyzed	Biofilm electrode interface
HR-TEM	Morphological & structural analysis	Nanostructure, biofilm-electrode contact	Visualizes nanostructures (e.g., CNTs, graphene), microbial adherence and spatial arrangement of conductive networks
XPS	Surface chemistry	Elemental composition & chemical bonding states	Identifies functional groups (–OH, –COOH) promoting microbial adhesion and redox interactions
XANES	Local electronic structure	Oxidation state and local coordination	Reveals redox-active sites; monitors chemical changes during biofilm formation or operation
SEM	Surface morphology	Micro-scale surface texture	Observes biofilm growth patterns and 3DP layer fidelity
AFM	Topography & mechanical properties	Surface roughness, elasticity	Measures nanoscale roughness influencing bacterial adhesion
EIS	Electrochemical performance	Charge transfer resistance, capacitance	Quantifies interfacial resistance and ion transport limitations

AFM = atomic force microscopy; EIS = electrochemical impedance spectroscopy; HR-TEM = high-resolution transmission electron microscopy; OMFC = osmotic microbial fuel cell; SC = supercapacitor; SEM = scanning electron microscopy; XANES = X-ray absorption near-edge structure; XPS = X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy.

reverse solute flux [6,24,25]. Using 3DP and CAD modeling, the researchers investigated the impact of material on the performance of membrane feed spacers in FO processes [6]. The membrane is printed using acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS), polypropylene (PP) and natural PLA for this purpose. Among these materials, PLA becomes specifically important because it is biodegradable, environmentally friendly and unlikely to be favorable for microbes [6,163]. The twisted, multi-layer, modified new designs were created using 3DP technology to produce spacers. Since then, few studies have used 3DP to create membrane spacers, although, the focus has been on developing new designs or determining whether various printing techniques can be used to produce spacers [6,14,103,154]. Fig. 5 shows the schematic of FO membrane mechanism during wastewater transport.

4.3.3. Reactor assembly

Most OMFC are designed primarily for water purification applications and the performance of these devices can be significantly impacted by the type of reactor architecture used and the adequate flow and hydrodynamics (such as mass transfer within biofilms). Therefore, optimizing the system's shape, working volume and fluid inlet/outlet settings are crucial. Because of the greater effective exposed area, an MFC with a drop-like shape might function better relative to a square shape MFC [164]. Additionally, by reducing the dead zones where the flow velocity is less than 5% of the maximum velocity, adding baffles to the anode chamber may increase the voltage output in the MFC [21,26,104]. Table 4 summarizes the 3DP biodegradable material used for the fiber fabrication of OMFC components. Biocompatible materials are preferred for the development of OMFC because they offer superior platforms for the attachment and growth of biofilms. FDM was utilized to build MFC reactors with a high accuracy using nontoxic, biocompatible PLA. The quality of the 3DP single-chamber MFC reactor was identical to that of the traditional acrylic fiber material. In addition, reactor shapes can then be printed again to create an OMFC system, proving that 3DP has created many opportunities for reactor upscaling and stacking OMFC designs [16,31].

In order to effectively integrate SC with 3DP OMFC-SC, a reactor design must carefully balance ion transport, fluid dynamics, electrode accessibility and structural scalability. Improved substrate-biofilm interactions and reduced diffusion gradients can be achieved by the reactor architecture by encouraging unidirectional or controlled laminar flow across the anode chamber. Vertical or radial configurations that enhance the electrode surface-to-volume ratio and reduce the overall footprint are made possible by the integration of 3DP stacked cell modules, enabling modular and scalable designs [66,71,86,95]. For the anode chamber to facilitate the growth of biofilms and effective electron transfer pathways, 3DP porous conductive scaffolds with engineered tortuosity are commonly used. Hydrophilic or hydrophobic membranes may be present on the cathode side to facilitate osmotic

potential generation or selective ion exchange; CEM are frequently used in conjunction with the salt bridge. Interstitial zones, either internally embedded or externally coupled, allow for the simultaneous harvesting and storage of energy in SC. In order to maximize the electron flux from the bioanode to the storage unit and reduce impedance mismatch, these zones ought to be designed. Materials (such as PLA or ABS) reinforced with conductive fillers or coatings can be 3DP to create reactor chamber walls that guarantee electrical isolation and chemical stability. Optimizing flow regimes, pressure drops and ion diffusion pathways can be done through multi-physics modeling and computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations. Additionally, simple scaling, maintenance and component replacement are made possible by modular plug-and-play architecture.

A scalable and effective energy harvesting system is revealed by the performance analysis of stacked OMFC units combined with SC energy storage. Effective stacking strategies allow the OMFC units to scale from a single 100 mL reactor to larger volumes (1–10 L), increasing daily energy generation and total power output proportionately. The produced energy is stored in SC with a high energy density of $0.0564 \text{ Wh cm}^{-3}$ (50 F cm^{-3} at 2.85 V); a single OMFC requires about 70–80 cells, while a 10 L stack may require up to 7000–8000 cells. In real-world applications like field-level bioenergy systems and pilot-scale wastewater treatment, this storage system ensures continuous operation and dependability by effectively buffering the bioelectricity with additional safety margins (10–15% losses). The integration shows great promise for modular and sustainable energy solutions. Table 8 depict the projected techno-economic analysis of OMFC-SC system.

Notwithstanding encouraging developments, 3DP OMFC-SC systems still have a number of significant issues that restrict their long-term feasibility and industrial scalability. The durability and material compatibility of 3DP parts in the severe biological and electrochemical conditions common to OMFC operations are a big worry. Even when loaded with conductive fillers, commonly used materials like PLA or ABS are susceptible to mechanical degradation, biofouling, or loss of conductivity as a result of extended exposure to moisture, salinity, pH changes and microbiological activity [165,166]. Surface coatings like metal oxides, graphene, or polyaniline can improve performance, but over time, they frequently experience delamination, decreased stability, or incompatibility with specific microorganisms [165,167]. Therefore, there is an urgent need for printable composites that are both intrinsically conductive and biocompatible. Some instances of these include PEDOT:PSS blends and CNT-hydrogel hybrids, which can sustain biofilm growth while withstanding operational stress.

Scalability is yet another enduring barrier, despite enabling intricate, modular OMFC designs, low printing speeds, expensive materials and a lack of process standardization limit the use of 3D printing on a larger scale. On large-scale manufacturing, processes such as FDM and DIW are especially slow and the necessary conductive inks or

Fig. 4. Schematic of benefits of electrodes: non-3DP and 3DP techniques (a, b and c) non 3DP electrodes (real and microscopic images) [148], (d and f) 3DP abiotic electrode [32], (e) 3DP biotic electrodes for OMFC-SC system [17] and (g) EET mechanism in OMFC system for anode and cathode electrode. EET = extracellular electron transfer; OMFC = osmotic microbial fuel cell; SC = supercapacitor.

filaments, which are frequently made of carbon, silver, or graphene, are still far more costly than conventional graphite plates or stainless-steel mesh [23,110,168]. In addition, it is still difficult to maintain uniform print quality, conductivity and dimensional accuracy across big batches in the absence of automated quality control systems or industrial-grade multi-nozzle platforms. The high initial cost of 3D printing equipment and the specialized materials needed to create long-lasting OMFC-SC components present major obstacles to economic viability when compared to traditional manufacturing techniques. Even though techno-economic models predict cost savings from labor savings and local sourcing, the cost of 3DP OMFC stacks is still higher per unit than their

bulk-produced counterparts [19]. It will take recyclable materials, process optimization and possibly hybrid manufacturing techniques that combine 3D printing with moulding or laser sintering to close this gap.

Finally, even though 3DP bio-anodes embed active microbial populations directly into the electrode matrix, allowing for quick start-up times, it is still difficult to maintain biofilm stability and performance over time. Decreased current output may result from biofilm thinning, contamination and adhesion loss over time. Improved start-up and retention have been shown in studies employing synthetic biofilms. However, maintaining these improvements in dynamic wastewater

Fig. 5. Schematic of FO membrane with and without fouling (a and b) FO created by 3DP methods (c) FO membrane after fouling [6]. FO = forward osmosis.

conditions still necessitates more innovation, especially in the areas of microstructure electrode surfaces, quorum-sensing improvements and nutrient diffusion control.

5. Future outlook and applications

5.1. Advancement in 3DP techniques

The use of 3DP to fabricate OMFC-SC systems is a promising development in the quest for sustainable energy and effective wastewater treatment. High-precision, customizable OMFC-SC components with complex geometries, optimized porosity and increased surface area can be produced using 3DP, as evidenced by recent advancements in additive manufacturing. These characteristics are essential for enhancing bioelectrochemical performance. A distinct advantage over conventional

manufacturing techniques is the ability to fabricate intricately structured electrodes that improve microbial adhesion and electron transfer kinetics thanks to the design flexibility made possible by 3DP. AM is a useful technique for speeding up the deployment of OMFC-SC in experimental and pilot-scale applications, especially once live bacterial colonies are integrated into biotic electrodes during the process. This enhances charge transport dynamics and facilitates faster start-up (Fig. 4) [13,21,98].

5.2. Engineering limitations and material challenges

Despite these benefits, widespread adoption is hampered by a number of significant issues. Significant limitations are presented by the high price and poor electrochemical durability of commercially available 3D-printable materials. The majority of printable polymers are not biocompatible or conductible enough to sustain microbial activity over

Table 8
Techno-economic analysis of stacked OMFC-SC system

Parameters	Single OMFC unit	Stacked OMFC	Stacked OMFC	Stacked OMFC
Volume per unit	100 mL	1 L (10 units)	5 L (50 units)	10 L (100 units)
Power density (W m ⁻³)	35–40	38–45	42–50	45–55
Anode and cathode area (m ²)	0.0036 and 0.0056 (carbon cloth and graphite rod respectively)			
Power output per unit (W)	0.165–0.188	1.65–1.88	8.25–9.40	16.5–18.80
Energy per Day per Unit (Wh)	3.96–4.51	39.6–45.1	198–225.5	396–451
Energy Density (Wh L ⁻¹)	39.6–45.1			
SC Energy Density (Wh cm ⁻³)	~ 0.0564			
No. of SC Needed	1	2–3	10–12	20–23
Stacking Strategy	Single unit	Parallel for high current	Modular: 5 × 1 L stacks	Modular: 10 × 1 L stacks
Remark	Compact high-output design	Suitable for pilot scale	Semi-industrial scale	Pilot plant or field test level

OMFC = osmotic microbial fuel cell; SC = supercapacitor.

Fig. 6. Schematic of various applications of OMFC-SC system. OMFC = osmotic microbial fuel cell; SC = supercapacitor.

an extended period of time. Graphene, carbon nanotubes and metal oxides are examples of conductive nanomaterials that are being embedded within polymer matrices to improve mechanical and electrochemical performance in order to overcome these limitations [11]. However, more research is needed to address problems like interfacial stability, long-term degradation and material homogeneity. Furthermore, to guarantee microbial affinity, surface conductivity and structural integrity, it will be crucial to comprehend the thermomechanical behavior of multi-material (MM) inks and optimize post-processing methods [110].

5.3. Integration of smart materials and artificial intelligence (AI)

Furthermore, the functionality and scalability of OMFC-SC systems could be greatly increased by combining smart materials with AI. The dynamic regulation of microbial adhesion and detachment provided by stimulus-responsive materials (such as thermo-, pH- and redox-sensitive polymers) may lessen biofouling and enhance long-term performance. Through engineering these materials to change their hydrophobicity or surface charge in response to environmental cues, tunable electrode interfaces that are suited to particular microbial communities can be produced. Simultaneously, real-time operational parameter monitoring and optimization are made possible by AI-driven system control. Complex datasets from integrated sensors can be processed by machine learning (ML) algorithms to forecast biofilm growth, identify anomalies and automatically modify feed cycles, flow rates, or resistance, improving stability and power output [12]. AI can reduce trial-and-error in 3DP design by using ML models like Bayesian optimization and genetic algorithms to predict ideal print parameters and material configurations from sparse datasets.

Stimuli-responsive polymers are becoming a viable alternative for enhancing self-maintenance and dependability. If the electrode temperature is pulsed above 32 °C, thermo-switchable poly(N-isopropylacrylamide) (PNIPAm) can shed matured biofilms, whereas

ferrocene-grafted alginate hydrogels respond to electrode potential by modifying their redox state and, consequently, their charge-transfer resistance. Direct contact is strengthened and DET is accelerated by magneto-responsive composites that contain FeO₄ nanoparticles, which allow external magnetic fields to orient electroactive bacteria towards the electrode. These smart materials can suppress biofouling without the need for chemical cleaning by adjusting hydrophobicity, surface charge, or proton conductivity in situ. This allows biofilms to remain within an ideal metabolic window [169,170].

5.4. MM-3DP functional grading

The design of functionally graded electrodes with spatial variations in porosity, conductivity and catalytic activity is made possible by the combination of MM-3DP and AI technologies. Better charge distribution is the outcome of these sophisticated geometries improved directional electron flow and nutrient transport. Creating hierarchical porous electrodes through extrusion-based and inkjet-assisted 3DP techniques has already shown promise in promoting substrate diffusion and lowering internal resistance [109]. Future research must establish the relationship between print parameters (such as nozzle diameter, print speed and layer height) and performance metrics in order to achieve the best electrochemical performance. Further research is still needed in the areas of rheological control, long-term durability and ink compatibility under electrochemical operating conditions.

5.5. Global energy and climate challenge

The growing worldwide energy and climate crisis emphasizes the need for reliable, effective OMFC-SC systems. More than 78% of the world's energy consumption, or about 18 TW, still comes from fossil fuels as of 2023 [114]. About 90% of anthropogenic global warming is caused by GHG, especially CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O [171]. These gases cause global temperatures to rise, heatwaves to get worse and hydrological

cycles to be upset. Energy demands for crop management, water treatment and cooling are increased by roughly 7% for every 1 °C increase in global temperature [172,173]. These statistics demonstrate the need for decentralized, renewable technologies like OMFC-SC, which offer the benefits of simultaneous resource recovery, water treatment and electricity generation. Particularly if combined with 3DP and intelligent control systems, OMFC-SC technologies hold great promise for implementation in remote, off-grid, or disaster-prone regions lacking conventional infrastructure.

5.6. Techno-economic considerations for 3DP materials

The cost and material characteristics of printable inks continue to be a barrier to commercialization, despite the fact that 3D printing provides OMFC-SC fabrication with scalability and design flexibility. Such as the biodegradable thermoplastic PLA is used extensively because it is inexpensive (around \$20–30/kg), easy to extrude and environmentally friendly [174]. However, as PLA is not electrically conductive by nature, it frequently needs to be post-processed or conductive fillers added. However, despite their superior electrical and electrochemical capabilities, graphene-based inks can be prohibitively expensive for large-scale applications, with prices ranging from \$300 to \$500/g [175]. Furthermore, it is still technically difficult to achieve stable dispersion and printability of graphene in polymer matrices. Techno-economic trade-offs must therefore be considered: although inexpensive materials such as PLA are perfect for structural elements, hybrid formulations (such as graphene PLA composites) may be needed for critical electroactive layers in order to balance cost, conductivity and print fidelity. Optimizing ink rheology and creating scalable synthesis techniques for inexpensive conductive nanomaterials could greatly lower costs and encourage wider use of 3DP-enabled OMFC-SC systems [174,176]. Fig. 6 represents the various applications of OMFC-SC system.

6. Conclusions

Globally, the excessive use of fossil fuels, such as coal, wood, diesel, gasoline and other petrochemical products, is contributing to the depletion of natural resources and an increment in global warming. Thus, the development of sustainable and ecologically friendly technology that can replace the current natural resources is essential. Furthermore, wastewater treatment is essential due to its harmful effects on the environment. In this regard, the recent advancements in 3DP technology have led to an increase in the use of 3DP in OMFC. The literature has demonstrated the potential of 3DP, a fast and precise fabrication process that can be utilized for fabrication of different OMFC components with improved efficiency. Significantly, 3DP may change the intricate geometric configurations of the FO membranes and electrodes in the OMFC system. Specific characteristics, such as modified geometry of high flux membrane and more porous electrode structure, increase the overall efficiency of OMFC systems. SC is a simple, efficient and cost-effective way to extract energy from the 3DP stacked OMFC system without the need for additional electronics management. Hence, more research should look into such possibilities for the best possible design and manufacture of 3DP parts, particularly for stacked OMFC systems. Also, by accelerating the process of optimizing custom designs and new materials for the entire system, 3DP can be a great tool for the commercialization of OMFC technology. It is beneficial in markets such as the energy and desalination sector, with a strong need for precision, customization, flexibility and complex designs. Furthermore, 3DP stacked assembly can reduce or eliminate the need for additional components such as complex structural components, resulting in more reasonably priced, better and dependable performance with a decreased possibility of human error. Therefore, 3DP will be able to forefront the commercialization of OMFC-SC technology through the use of innovative biodegradable materials and designs.

Author contributions

Conceptualization: Mandar S. Bhagat and Chirag Mevada. Methodology: Mandar S. Bhagat and Chirag Mevada. Writing– original draft: Mandar S. Bhagat and Chirag Mevada. Writing–review and editing: Mandar S. Bhagat and Chirag Mevada. Supervision: Mandar S. Bhagat and Chirag Mevada. Funding acquisition: Chirag Mevada.

Data availability statement

The datasets generated during and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no potential conflicts of interest regarding this article's research, authorship, and publication.

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